

CONTEXTUAL REALIZATION OF THE DERIVATIONAL AND FUNCTIONAL SUFFIXES IN ENGLISH

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Annotation

This article explores the development of functional-derivational potential of English word-formation. The English language is known for its wonderful quality of the way in which words and sentences are formed and used. Formation of new words from an existing root word by adding suffixes and prefixes. In this article we will talk how the addition of suffixes usually changes the word class of the particular word.

Keywords: Derivation, inflection, affix, paradigm, lexical meaning, formation, meaning, homonyms.

Аннотация

В данной статье исследуется развитие функционально-деривационного потенциала английского словообразования. Английский язык известен своим замечательным качеством формирования и использования слов и предложений. Образование новых слов из существующего корневого слова путем добавления суффиксов и приставок. В этой статье мы поговорим о том, как добавление суффиксов обычно меняет класс конкретного слова.

Ключевые слова: Деривация, словоизменение, аффикс, парадигма, лексическое значение, образование, значение, омонимы.

Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola ingliz tilidagi so'z yasalishining funktsional-derivatsion salohiyatining rivojlanishini o'rganadi. Ingliz tili so'z va jumalarni yaratish va ishlatish usulining ajoyib sifati bilan mashhur. Mavjud o`zak so`zdan qo`shimcha va old qo`shimchalar qo`shib yangi so`z yasash. Ushbu maqolada biz

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qo'shimchalar qo'shilishi odatda ma'lum bir so'zning so'z sinfini qanday o'zgartirishi haqida gapiramiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Tuzatish, fleksiya, affiks, paradigma, leksik ma'no, shakllanish, ma'no, omonimlar.

Lexicology is primarily concerned with derivational affixes, the other group being the domain of grammarians. The derivational affixes in fact, as well as the whole problem of word – formation form a boundary area between lexicology and grammar and are therefore studied in both.

Language being a system in which the elements of vocabulary and grammar are closely interrelated, our study of affixes cannot be complete without some discussion of the similarity and difference between derivational and functional morphemes.

The similarity is obvious as they are so often homonymous. Otherwise the two groups are essentially different because they render different types of meaning.

Functional affixes serve to convey grammatical meaning. They build different forms of one and the same word. A word – form or the form of a word, is defined as one of the different aspects a word may take as a result of inflection patterns. Complete sets of well the various forms of a word when considered as inflectional patterns, such as declensions or conjugations are termed paradigms.

A paradigm is therefore defined as the system of grammatical forms characteristic of a word.

Near, nearer, nearest

Son, son's, sons', sons

Derivational affixes serve to supply the stem with components of lexical and lexico – grammatical meaning and thus form different words. One and the same lexico – grammatical meaning of the affix is sometimes accompanied by different combinations of various lexical meanings. Thus, the lexico – grammatical meaning supplied by the suffix – y consists in the ability to express the qualitative idea

peculiar to adjectives and creates adjectives from noun stems. The lexical meanings of the same suffix are somewhat variegated: ‘full of’ as in bushy or cloudy; ‘composed of’ as in stony; ‘having the quality of’ as in slangy; ‘resembling’ as in baggy and some more. This suffix sometimes conveys emotional components of meaning.

A derivative is always capable of further derivation and is therefore homonymous to a stem. Foolish for instance is derived from the stem fool – and is homonymous to a stem foolish – occurring in the word’s foolishness and foolishly. Inflected word ceases to be homonymous to stems. No further derivation is possible from the word – forms fools, where the stem fool – is followed by the functional affix – s. Inflected words are neither structurally nor functionally be equivalent to the morphologically simple words belonging to the same part of speech. Things are different from business functionally because the two words cannot occur in identical can texts and structurally, because of the different character of their immediate constituents and different word – forming possibilities.

The semantic and functional difference that has already been stated is supported by statistical properties and difference in valency.

Of the three main types of morphemes, namely roots derivational affixes and functional formatives, the roots are by far the most numerous. They are many thousand roots in English the derivational affixes, when listed, do not go beyond a few scores. The list given in Chamber’s Huventuth Century Dictionary takes up five pages and a half, comprising all the detailed explanations of their origin and meaning and even then, the actual living suffixes are much fewer. As to the functional formatives, there are hardly more than ten of them. Regular English verbs, for instance have only four forms:

Play, plays, played, playing

as a compared to the German verbs which have as many as sixteen.

The valency of these three groups of morphemes is naturally in inverse proportion to their number. Functional affixes can be opened with a few exceptions, to any element belonging to the part of speech they serve.

The regular correlation of singular and plural forms of nouns can serve to illustrate this point. Thus heart – hearts, boy – boys. The relics of archaic forms such as child – children or foreign plurals like criterion – criteria are very few in comparison with these.

Derivational affixes do not combine so freely and regularly. The suffix – en occurring in golden and leaden cannot be added to the root steel. Nevertheless, as their correlations are never isolated and always contain more than two opposition's boy – boyish, child – childish, gold – golden, lead – leaden, wood – wooden. The valency of roots is of a very different order and the oppositions may be sometimes isolated. It is for instance difficult to find another pair with the root heart and the same relationship as in heart – sweetheart.

Knowing the plural inflectional suffix – s we know how the countable nouns are inflected. The probability of a mistake is not great.

With derivational affixes the situation is much more intricate. Knowing, for instance, the complete list of affixes of feminization, formation of feminine nouns from the stems of masculine ones by adding a characteristic suffix, we shall be able to recognize a new word if we know the root. This knowledge, however, will not enable us to construct words acceptable for English vocabulary, because derivational affixes are attached to their particular stems in a haphazard and unpredictable manner. Why for instance, is it impossible to call a ladyguest a guestless on the pattern of host – hostless? Note also:

Lion – lioness, tiger – tigress, but bear – she bear, elephant – she elephant, wolf – she wolf.

very often the correlation is assured by suppletion, therefore we have:

boar – sow, buck – doe, bull – cow, cook – hen, ram – ewe.

On the whole this state of things is more or less common to many languages; but English has stricter constraints in this respect than, for example in English is very narrow.

After having devoted special attention to the difference in statistical characteristics of the various kinds of morphemes. We shall also notice that they are different positionally. A functional affix marks the word boundary, it can only follow the affix of derivation and come last, so that no further derivation is possible for a stem *t* which a functional affix is added. That is why functional affixes are called by E.Nida the outer formatives as contrasted to the which is equivalent to our term derivational affixes.

It might be argued that the outer position of functional affixes is disproved by such examples as the disabled, the unwanted. It must be noted, however, that in these words – *ed* is not a functional affix, it receives derivational force so that disabled is not a form of the verb to disable, but a new word – a collective noun.

To sum up: derivational and functional morphemes may happen to be identical in sound form, but they are substantially different in meaning, function, valency, statistical characteristics.

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